

FUNDAMENTALS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF AXIOLOGICAL COMPETENCE AMONG TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Currently, one of the main areas of leading universities in the country consists in the development of professional and specialty skills in order to improve the skills of specialists in various types of activities, as well as competencies based on their axiological approach. The author spoke in this article about ways to improve the effectiveness of Education based on a competent approach in the system of professional development.*

Keywords: *axiology, competence, educational efficiency, didactic approach, pedagogical competence.*

For the training of managerial qualified personnel for the educational sphere, it is of paramount importance for them to acquire managerial knowledge and skills based on competency and personal-oriented approaches. The solution of this task is facilitated by the development of a methodological system for the formation of professional-managerial, pedagogical, psychological and value (axiological) competence in the field of education in a targeted manner and their introduction into the process of professional retraining.

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The educational process in the system of professional retraining and professional development of specialists of various specialties is aimed at expanding the activities related to knowledge, activating their intelligence and cultural, spiritual values and moral standards, promoting the formation of the personality of a modern leader in the field of Education. In order to avoid mistakes in the performance of professional obligations and carry out managerial activities at a high level, it is imperative that a leader in the field of education of any level has a formed professional-managerial competence.

-When comparing the trends identified in the study of the practice of preparing teachers for professional development in higher educational institutions, one can rely on:

- between the modern requirements for strengthening the guiding personnel in the field of education of society and methodological approaches to training personnel in a higher professional educational institution, the absence of a theoretical basis;

-allows educators to disclose a set of contradictions between the need to develop an educational system based on a competent and personal-oriented approach and the existing didactic master classes in the application of innovative technologies of Education.

To eliminate the indicated contradictions, it will be important to analyze the achievements of psychological and pedagogical science, to develop student competencies in the field of education in higher educational institutions.

L.M. Mitina accordance with the scientific definition of mitina, "pedagogical competence includes knowledge, qualifications, skills, as well as methods and ways of their realization in the activities, communication, development (self-development) of a person." L.M.Mitina defines two structureasti in the structure of pedagogical competence of a pedagogical: active (knowledge of the implementation of pedagogical activity, transverse, qualification and methods) and communicative (knowledge, skills, skills and methods of carrying out pedagogical communication).

The functional aspect of the descriptions of the structure and content of pedagogical competence includes not only knowledge, qualifications, skills, but also the methods of conducting the pedagogical process itself. At the moment, the communicative aspect is rich in knowledge, skills, skills and methods of implementing pedagogical forms of communication between the teacher and the student. The second component of pedagogical competence, like the first, is also interrelated.

Competence will not be the sum of knowledge and qualifications, after all, the degree of its manifestation depends on the conditions, that is, especially pedagogical conditions. Having a whole list of competencies means, first of all, being able to use the existing experience and understand the situation under specific conditions.

Competence is a set of activation of knowledge, qualifications and moral characteristics that the educator uses in specific activities in relation to students. Similar competencies make it known that it is all professional types of pedagogical activity that are calculated. the main ones from general competence are: adaptation, socialization, introduction into society and personal self-realization.

In this sense, the strategy for improving educational tactics in modern public and cultural situations should be described by the following idea: a qualitatively new level of preparation and upbringing with the help of improving their general competencies is achieved on the basis of updating the harmonious interaction of human – society – nature systems.

The main task in the system of professional development of educators should be the independent management of one's own practice and self-control skills. A necessary and sufficient condition for the qualification of self-control is the following:

1. Definition of concepts (accumulation of knowledge and experience of movement in modern conditions);
2. Formation of moral (axiological)values \ u200b \ u200bof pedagogy (the attitude of the educator to other individuals and the environment);
3. Moral standard (development in the pedagogical of moral qualifications for successful interaction with the environment in the modern world).

The essence of reflective qualities on the basis of professional competence

Table 1.

№	Types of competence	Adjectives
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1	psychological competence	to be able to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize a positive dialogue with students and other participants in the educational process, to be able to timely understand and overcome various negative psychological conflicts;
2	methodological competence	is the methodological rational organization of the pedagogical process, the correct establishment of forms of educational or educational activity, the ability to select methods and Means for their intended purpose, the effective application of methods, the successful application of means;
3	technological competence	to have psychological, methodological, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence
4	informational competence	search, collection, sorting, processing and targeted, appropriate, effective use of necessary, important, necessary, useful information in an information environment;
5	creative competence	is a critical, creative approach to pedagogical activity, to be able to demonstrate the competence of one's own creativity;
	communicative competence	is the ability to sincerely communicate with all participants in the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive effect on them.

The personal-oriented model of professional development of pedagogical personnel in the transition to competency-oriented education makes it possible to increase the functioning, communicative and personal aspects of the competence of pedagogical personnel and the entire pedagogical team through a personal-oriented, axiological and technological approach to its organization. As we analyze the dynamics of professional competence, in which the growth of some significant basic competencies is reflected in each allocated group of educators, we can conclude about the effectiveness of the model applied to the professional development of pedagogical personnel.

- Obtaining objective information on the progress of pedagogical activity and the development of the pedagogical personality is a prerequisite for the transition to the competence of professional education and the successful conduct of modernization of Education.
- As a result of the set of management methods used by the methodological service and monitoring of professional development at the stage of transition to competency-oriented education, positive changes have occurred in the development of pedagogical activity:
 - professional development of each educator as a pedagogical team in a separate way;
 - to monitor the level of development of the professional activities of the entire pedagogical team and its members in order to make effective management decisions;
 - identification of typical difficulties of educators, determination of the level of qualification (high, medium, low) of professional Lyceum pedagogical workers for each qualification category on the basis of the standard "teacher of production education;
 - construction by the methodological service of the main areas of work for all pedagogical workers, taking into account their belonging to a particular group, and for each in an individual way – the trajectory of self-development;

- creation of a complex system for increasing the professional competence of engineering and pedagogical workers with the consideration of their personal and professional descriptions;
- the influence of methodological and socio-psychological services on the personal development of the educator, and through it on the pedagogical system of the entire Lyceum and, in part, on the positive development of students.

Thus, we promote the development of professionally significant personal qualities and abilities that lead educators to self-creative realization in the profession and the development of competence in students in the process of professional development work from the monitoring procedure, while creating an adapted developing personal-oriented environment:

- It is necessary to build education taking into account the main directions of its technologization, which requires a special organization of the process of professional development with the pedagogical team, the appointment of the essence and management of professional development of educators will consist in the development of pedagogical activity and the personality of the educator, the formation of the readiness of educators

- It was substantiated that the problem of retraining teachers working at the stage of transition to competency-oriented education has relevance.

Organization of professional development on the basis of monitoring in a mandatory manner requires an analysis of the level of professional competence previously achieved by educators, the image of expected changes and the presence of ways of transition to a new state.

Organization of professional development of a group of educators with different pedagogical experience and education through mastering pedagogical technologies allows to increase the efficiency of methodological work by modeling a personal-oriented approach to its organization, monitoring of administrative management of pedagogical professional development, the progress of the development of pedagogical activity, obtaining objective information about the pedagogical personality is a prerequisite for successful

- monitoring of the educational process is a necessary element of successful management of the development of pedagogical activity, aimed at ensuring the correctional and prognostic orientation of the professional development of teachers by mastering pedagogical technologies, increasing the quality of professional education, since the mastery of pedagogical technologies leads to the improvement of the educational process.

Determination of the correlation of pedagogical difficulties and typology of pedagogical technologies for their elimination; it is advisable to improve the set of tools to clarify the purpose of professional development of pedagogical personnel by comparing pedagogical technologies and student competencies that ensure their formation.

Plans for improving the qualifications of a group of teachers with different levels of competence, experience and education; the development of methodological support for personal-oriented methodological work, recommendations for drawing up individual plans for the development of pedagogues and the entire pedagogical community can contribute to the development of axiological competence in educators. This may include the search and formation of other ways to increase the axiological competence of educators and the formation of their competencies.

The problem of influencing the level of axiological competence on the effectiveness of the pedagogical process, in particular, on the development of the student's personality and the formation of their competence, requires in-depth study.

Theoretical studies and analysis of educational practice show that one of the effective ways to improve qualifications is training with an orientation to the possibility of students. In addition to the availability of a number of scientific and practical works related to initiative and propaganda of student opportunities, the level of technologies, concepts and principles of pedagogical education should be emphasized.

Its essence is as follows:

1) the increased need of the educator for self-actualization at the level of personal-oriented education in the absence of theoretical and methodological development of facilitation and the necessary morality in the system of professional development of pedagogical personnel;

2) the need to develop in the system of professional development the normative, technocratic model of education and the orientation of pedagogical education towards the long-term effect of education to the individual, as well as the concepts of axiological competence of students;

3) the pedagogical practice of professional development, standards, the need to resolve the objective conflict between the views on what educational results of educational programs are considered a civil society and a knowledge-based economy.

REFERENCES

1. Drapeau Patti. Sparking student creativity (practical ways to promote innovative thinking and problem solving). – Alexandria – Virginia, USA: ASCD, 2014.
2. Ismailova Z., Ximmataliyev D., Choriyeu R., Mustafoyeva D., Xashimova M., Ochilova G., Fayzullayev R., Berdaliyeva G., “The Forensic Professional Education Teacher Mediacompetery Development Technology”//International Journal of Health Sciences Vol. 6 No. 2, August 2022, pages: 1189-1205.
3. Natalie Denmeade. Gamification with Moodle. Packt Publishing - ebooks Account 2015. - 134 pp.
4. Paul Kim. Massive Open Online Courses: The MOOC Revolution. Routledge; 1 edition 2014. - 176 pp.
5. William Rice. Moodle E-Learning Course Development - Third Edition. Packt Publishing - ebooks Account; 3 edition 2015. - 350 pp.
6. Diehl Michael, Stroebe, Wolfgang. Productivity Loss in Idea-Generating Groups: Tracking Down the Blocking Effect // Journal of Personality and Social Psychology 61 (3). – 1991.P.392–403.